

**AT3B Review of Evidence: Strengthening Evidence
Use in Environmental Policy: A Rapid Review of
Science-Policy Relationships Across OECD Nations**

ENS5010 – Global Challenges and Sustainability

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Introduction:

Part B responds to the evidence-integration issues identified in Part A's assessment of *Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037*. Part A found that evidence is not always presented with sufficient transparency, consistency, or empirical support, identifying weaknesses including limited empirical detail, reliance on assumption-driven modelling, limited evidence of independent peer review, and weak outcome evidence for monitoring, evaluation and biodiversity offset performance (Department of Environment, Land, Water & Planning, 2017). These weaknesses suggest that the issue is not only whether evidence exists, but how institutions integrate that evidence into policy and sustain its credibility over time. This rapid review therefore examines whether formalised science-policy relationships improve evidence use in environmental policy development.

Using the PICO framework (see Table 1), this rapid review asks: To what extent do formalised institutional relationships between scientific advisors and policy departments, compared with weaker, informal, or absent advisory arrangements, improve the use of scientific evidence in environmental policy development across Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) member nations?

Table 1. PICO framework for Rapid Review

PICO element	Meaning in this review
P – Population	Environmental policy development across OECD nations
I – Intervention	Formalised institutional relationships between scientific advisors and policy departments
C – Comparison	Weaker, informal, or absent advisory arrangements
O – Outcome	Improved use of scientific evidence

In this review, formalised institutional relationships are understood as structured science-policy interfaces (SPIs) through which “relations between scientists and other actors in the policy process” enable exchange, interpretation, and the “joint construction of knowledge” for decision-making (van den Hove, 2007, p. 807). These relationships may include science advisory committees, government science advisors, academics, and knowledge-brokering roles. Gluckman et al. (2021) describe modern science advice as operating through an ecosystem of “commissions, committees, academies, and/or science advisors”, which inform

policy options without directly determining political decisions (p. 2). Importantly, scientific evidence refers primarily to “systematic research” used to inform policy development, evaluation, and decision-making (Head, 2008, p. 1). This distinction is important because evidence can guide policy, but it does not remove the values, trade-offs, and political conclusions that shape decision-making.

This question matters because environmental policy outcomes involve interconnected ecological, social, political, and economic systems, in which uncertainty and competing values shape how evidence is used and interpreted. Oliver et al. (2014) identify access to research, clarity of findings, and timing as major factors shaping evidence uptake, while institutional relationships and knowledge-brokering arrangements are common facilitators. In environmental governance, persistent barriers such as insufficient engagement training, academic reward structures, and weak evaluation of knowledge-exchange outcomes can “prevent or reduce the uptake of scientific knowledge into decision-making processes” (Cvitanovic et al., 2025, p. 2). Formalised relationships may therefore improve evidence access, translation, and integration by producing advice that is easier for decision-makers to utilise effectively in policy (Cvitanovic et al., 2025; Oliver et al., 2014). However, if poorly designed or insufficiently transparent, they may also narrow the evidence base or reduce independent scrutiny, particularly where brokerage lacks “trust”, “transparency”, “legitimacy”, and “respect for diverse knowledge systems” (Gluckman et al., 2021, p. 4). This review assesses whether formalised science-policy relationships can address the weaknesses identified in Biodiversity 2037.

Review Protocol

Methodological Approach

The PRISMA 2020 reporting principles guided the identification, screening, exclusion, and selection of records for data extraction (Page et al., 2021). A rapid review was chosen over a full systematic review to deliver a focused, timely synthesis (Dobbins, 2017). Shortcuts included using two academic databases, excluding grey literature, restricting results to English-language peer-reviewed literature published between 2010 and 2026, and having a single researcher complete all aspects of screening, data extraction, and appraisal. These shortcuts are addressed as limitations in the Results section.

Search Strategy

Scopus and Web of Science were selected because they provide broad coverage of peer-reviewed literature across environmental policy, sustainability, governance, and science-policy research. Searches were conducted in April 2026 using the database limits outlined above. Google Scholar and grey literature were excluded to keep the screening process manageable, replicable, and focused on peer-reviewed evidence. Search terms were developed from the PICO framework, with Boolean search strings mapped to each element of the research question (see Tables 2 and 3). These terms were combined into four searches across both databases, targeting SPIs, advisory bodies, knowledge brokers, and evidence-use outcomes in environmental and sustainability policy contexts. Full search strings are provided in Appendix A.

Table 2. Search Terms Aligned with the PICO Framework

PICO link	Search concept	Boolean search terms
Population	Environmental and sustainability policy	“environmental policy” OR “environmental governance” OR “sustainability policy”
Population	Biodiversity, climate, and natural resource policy	“biodiversity policy” OR “climate policy” OR “natural resource management”
Intervention	Science-policy interface	“science-policy interface” OR “science policy interface” OR “science-policy relationship”
Intervention	Scientific advice	“scientific advice” OR “science advice” OR “expert advice”
Intervention	Advisory arrangements	“scientific advisory” OR “science advisory” OR “advisory bod*” OR “advisory body”
Intervention	Knowledge brokering	“knowledge brokering” OR “knowledge broker*”
Intervention	Knowledge exchange, transfer, translation, and co-production	“knowledge exchange” OR “knowledge transfer” OR “knowledge translation” OR “co-production” OR “knowledge co-production”
Comparison/context	Policy actors and institutions	“policy” OR “policymak*” OR “policy maker*” OR “policy department*” OR “government agenc*” OR “public administration” OR “decision maker*” OR “public sector” OR “governance” OR “government”
Outcome	Evidence and research use	“evidence use” OR “evidence uptake” OR “research use” OR “knowledge use” OR “evidence-informed” OR “evidence-informed policy” OR “evidence-based” OR “evidence-based policy”
Outcome	Policy learning and knowledge utilisation	“policy learning” OR “research utilisation” OR “research utilization” OR “knowledge utilisation” OR “knowledge utilization”

Table 2. Search Strategy and Database Results

Search no.	Search Focus	Scopus	Web of Science
1	Science-policy interface + environmental policy + evidence-use terms	27	16
2	Science-policy interface + environmental policy + knowledge exchange/co-production	55	36
3	Advisory bodies/scientific advice + environmental policy + evidence-use terms	19	12
4	Narrow combined PICO search	16	11
Total		117	75

Screening Process

Records were imported into EndNote, duplicates removed, and 107 records were screened by title and abstract. Each record was labelled as include (green), exclude (red), or uncertain (orange). Records labelled include or uncertain were retained for full-text assessment. The remaining 44 full texts were assessed against the criteria, and 18 studies were included after the final reassessment. Detailed exclusion reasons are provided in Appendix B.

Inclusion criteria required that studies were peer-reviewed, published in English between 2010 and 2026, focused on environmental or sustainability policy, and examined science-policy relationships, advisory arrangements, or structured evidence-use processes in OECD or comparable democratic policy contexts.

Table 3. Screening Flow

Stage	Number
Records identified from Scopus	117
Records identified from Web of Science	75
Total records identified	192
Duplicates removed	85
Records screened by title/abstract	107

Records excluded by title/abstract	63
Full texts assessed	44
Subtotal: full texts excluded	19
Final relevance/quality reassessment exclusions	7
Total full texts excluded after assessment and reassessment	26
Final studies included	18

Data Extraction and Quality Review

Data were extracted into a collation table that captured the country/policy context, science-policy relationship type, evidence-use outcome, key findings, and PICO relevance (see Appendix C). PRISMA 2020 was used as a reporting guide to improve transparency around extraction, study characteristics, outcomes, and quality appraisal (Page et al., 2021). Study quality was assessed using a traffic-light system evaluating clarity, relevance to environmental policy, alignment with the PICO question, and transparency of limitations (see Appendix B).

Results

Study Selection and Evidence Quality

Searches of Scopus and Web of Science identified 192 records. After 85 duplicates were removed, 107 records were screened by title and abstract, and 44 full texts were assessed. Following eligibility and relevance reassessment, 18 studies were included. The PRISMA flow diagram illustrating each stage of the screening and selection process is presented in Figure 1. Additionally, Appendix B lists exclusion reasons, and Appendix C presents the collation table, which systematically summarises the included studies' characteristics, quality ratings, and relevant findings. Fifteen studies were rated high quality under the traffic-light system, as they were peer-reviewed, highly relevant, and reported clear evidence-use outcomes. Three were rated moderate quality because they were more conceptual or had weaker outcome depth.

Figure 1. PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram of Study Identification, Screening, Eligibility Assessment, and Inclusion.

Key Findings

Collectively, most studies suggested that formalised science-policy relationships can improve the use of scientific evidence in environmental policy development. Evidence from statutory advisory arrangements emphasises that evidence uptake is stronger when advisory bodies have clear mandates, independence, institutional support, and access to decision-makers (Owens, 2012; Seibicke, 2025). Averchenkova et al. (2021a, 2021b) show that the UK Climate Change Act integrated expert advice into policy procedures through legally binding targets, carbon budgets, reporting obligations, and the Climate Change Committee, whose evidence was actively used in parliamentary debate to strengthen accountability and support evidence-informed climate policy.

A second pattern identified was that knowledge brokers, boundary organisations, and collaborative SPIs helped translate evidence into usable policy advice. Cvitanovic et al.

(2025), Dunn et al. (2018), Gilson et al. (2025), Kennedy (2018), Kaufman and Boxshall (2023), and Wagner et al. (2023) collectively demonstrate that these arrangements can improve communication between researchers and policymakers when built around trust, clear institutional purpose, adequate resources, and policy relevance. Pullin et al. (2016) further add that evidence is also more useful when methods are appropriate to policy needs, timelines, and uncertainty. Wagner et al. (2023) offer a strong empirical foundation because they evaluated 69 articles and 93 SPI cases, showing that SPIs frequently influence policy through social learning, agenda-setting, and policy formulation. This adds nuance by showing that SPIs often work less as direct “manuals for action” and more as mechanisms for shared understanding and evidence-informed decision-making (Wagner et al., 2023, p. 62).

The key exception was that formalised relationships alone did not guarantee evidence uptake. Runhaar and van Nieuwaal (2010) demonstrate this clearly, as evidence only became influential once the issue was reframed, dialogue between relevant stakeholders was strengthened, and legal or institutional conditions made science more usable in decision-making. Similarly, Richards (2019), Saarela and Söderman (2015), Greenhalgh et al. (2022), Lalor and Hickey (2014), Dupont et al. (2024), and Sundqvist and Linke (2024) highlight that evidence use depends on timely communication, credibility, trust, policy integration, and supportive political conditions. Taken together, formalised institutional relationships generally improve evidence use across OECD and comparable democratic contexts, but only where those relationships are independent, institutionally supported, and credible.

Limitations

Eight methodological shortcuts limit this rapid review: (1) single-researcher screening, extraction, and appraisal increased the risk of selection bias and subjective judgement (Page et al., 2021); (2) searching only Scopus and Web of Science may have missed relevant studies; (3) excluding Google Scholar may have reduced access to broader academic material; (4) excluding grey literature may have omitted government reports, policy evaluations, and other forms of evidence; (5) English-only articles may have underrepresented non-English OECD contexts; (6) the 2010-2026 date range may have excluded older foundational articles on science-policy relationships; (7) the traffic-light quality system lacked the detail of formal appraisal frameworks commonly used in systematic reviews; and (8) the broad policy scope made direct comparison difficult because included articles examined different policy contexts, institutions, and evidence-use processes. Future

reviews could implement multiple reviewers, a wider database coverage, grey literature, and formal risk-of-bias assessment. Accordingly, findings should be interpreted as provisional.

Conclusion

This rapid review finds that formalised science-policy relationships generally improve evidence use when they are independent, trusted, clearly mandated, and embedded in policy practice. However, formalisation alone is insufficient, as political conditions, institutional capacity, and credibility all affect the degree to which evidence informs policy. These findings should be interpreted cautiously, given the constraints of the rapid review process. For Biodiversity 2037, stronger advisory and knowledge-brokering structures could improve evidence transparency, integration, monitoring, and evaluation, provided they are grounded in independence, clear mandates, and institutional accountability. This suggests that improving evidence quality matters, but so do the institutions translating evidence into decisions.

References

- Averchenkova, A., Fankhauser, S., & Finnegan, J. (2021a). The impact of strategic climate legislation: Evidence from expert interviews on the UK Climate Change Act. *Climate Policy*, 21(2), 251–263. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2020.1819190>
- Averchenkova, A., Fankhauser, S., & Finnegan, J. (2021b). The influence of climate change advisory bodies on political debates: Evidence from the UK Committee on Climate Change. *Climate Policy*, 21(9), 1218–1233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2021.1878008>
- Cvitanovic, C., Karcher, D. B., Breen, J., Badullovich, N., Cairney, P., Dalla Pozza, R., Duggan, J., Hoffmann, S., Kelly, R., Meadow, A. M., & Posner, S. (2025). Knowledge brokers at the interface of environmental science and policy: A review of knowledge and research needs. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 163, Article 103973. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103973>
- Department of Environment, Land, Water and Planning. (2017). *Protecting Victoria's environment – Biodiversity 2037*. State Government of Victoria. <https://www.environment.vic.gov.au/biodiversityplan>
- Dobbins, M. (2017). *Rapid review guidebook: Steps for conducting a rapid review*. National Collaborating Centre for Methods and Tools. <https://www.nccmt.ca/tools/rapid-review-guidebook>
- Dunn, G., Bos, J. J., & Brown, R. R. (2018). Mediating the science-policy interface: Insights from the urban water sector in Melbourne, Australia. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 82, 143–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.02.001>
- Dupont, C., Rosamond, J., & Zaki, B. (2024). Investigating the scientific knowledge-policy interface in EU climate policy. *Policy & Politics*, 52(1), 88–107. <https://doi.org/10.1332/030557321x16861511996074>
- Gilson, G., Hovis, M., Gerlak, A. K., & Heikkila, T. (2025). Building the science-policy-practice interface: Insights from boundary organizations in the Colorado River Basin. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 172, Article 104212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104212>
- Gluckman, P. D., Bardsley, A., & Kaiser, M. (2021). Brokerage at the science-policy interface: From conceptual framework to practical guidance. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 8(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-021-00756-3>
- Greenhalgh, S., Müller, K., Thomas, S., Campbell, M. L., & Harter, T. (2022). Raising the voice of science in complex socio-political contexts: An assessment of contested water decisions.

Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning, 24(2), 242–260.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2021.2007762>

- Head, B. W. (2008). Three lenses of evidence-based policy. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 67(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8500.2007.00564.x>
- Kaufman, S., & Boxshall, A. (2023). Eleven enablers of science thought leadership to facilitate knowledge exchange in environmental regulation. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 147, 336–348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.06.018>
- Kennedy, E. (2018). Supporting scientific advice through a boundary organization. *Global Challenges*, 2(9), Article 1800018. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.201800018>
- Lalor, B., & Hickey, G. (2014). Strengthening the role of science in the environmental decision-making processes of executive government. *Organization & Environment*, 27(2), 161–180. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1086026614525641>
- Oliver, K., Innvar, S., Lorenc, T., Woodman, J., & Thomas, J. (2014). A systematic review of barriers to and facilitators of the use of evidence by policymakers. *BMC Health Services Research*, 14, Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-14-2>
- Owens, S. (2012). Experts and the environment: The UK Royal Commission on Environmental Pollution 1970–2011. *Journal of Environmental Law*, 24(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jel/eqr031>
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 134, 178–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2021.03.001>
- Pullin, A., Frampton, G., Jongman, R., Kohl, C., Livoreil, B., Lux, A., Pataki, G., Petrokofsky, G., Podhora, A., Saarikoski, H., Santamaria, L., Schindler, S., Sousa-Pinto, I., Vandewalle, M., & Wittmer, H. (2016). Selecting appropriate methods of knowledge synthesis to inform biodiversity policy. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 25(7), 1285–1300. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1131-9>
- Richards, G. (2019). The science-policy relationship hierarchy (SPRHi) model of co-production: How climate science organizations have influenced the policy process in Canadian case studies. *Policy Sciences*, 52(1), 67–95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-018-9328-2>

- Runhaar, H., & van Nieuwaal, K. (2010). Understanding the use of science in decision-making on cockle fisheries and gas mining in the Dutch Wadden Sea: Putting the science-policy interface in a wider perspective. *Environmental Science & Policy*, *13*(3), 239–248.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2010.03.001>
- Saarela, S., & Söderman, T. (2015). The challenge of knowledge exchange in national policy impact assessment: A case of Finnish climate policy. *Environmental Science & Policy*, *54*, 340–348.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.07.029>
- Seibicke, H. (2025). The institutional design of scientific advisory boards on climate change: A comparison at the intergovernmental, supranational, and national level. *Global Challenges*, *9*(9), Article e00371. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.202400371>
- Sundqvist, G., & Linke, S. (2024). Making science relevant: Comparing two science advisory organizations beyond the linear knowledge model. *Minerva*, *62*(4), 527–547.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11024-024-09528-0>
- van den Hove, S. (2007). A rationale for science-policy interfaces. *Futures*, *39*(7), 807–826.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2006.12.004>
- Wagner, N., Velandar, S., Biber-Freudenberger, L., & Dietz, T. (2023). Effectiveness factors and impacts on policymaking of science-policy interfaces in the environmental sustainability context. *Environmental Science & Policy*, *140*, 56–67.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.11.008>

Appendices

Appendix A: Full Boolean Search Strings

Table A1. Full Boolean Search Strings and Database Results for Scopus and Web of Science

Search no.	Search Focus	Full search string	Scopus	Web of Science
1	Science-policy interface + environmental policy + evidence-use terms	("science-policy interface" OR "science policy interface" OR "science-policy relationship" OR "science advice" OR "scientific advice") AND ("environmental policy" OR "environmental governance" OR "sustainability policy" OR "biodiversity policy" OR "climate policy") AND ("evidence use" OR "evidence uptake" OR "research use" OR "knowledge use" OR "knowledge exchange" OR "knowledge transfer" OR "knowledge translation" OR "evidence-informed")	27	16
2	Science-policy interface + environmental policy + knowledge exchange/co-production	("science-policy interface" OR "science policy interface" OR "science-policy relationship" OR "science advice" OR "scientific advice") AND ("environmental policy" OR "environmental governance" OR "sustainability policy" OR "biodiversity policy" OR "climate policy") AND ("knowledge exchange" OR "knowledge transfer" OR "knowledge translation" OR "co-production" OR "evidence-informed" OR "research use")	55	36
3	Advisory bodies/scientific advice + environmental policy + evidence-use terms	("scientific advice" OR "science advice" OR "scientific advisory" OR "science advisory" OR "advisory bod*" OR "expert advice") AND (policy OR policymak* OR "decision-making" OR governance OR government) AND ("evidence-informed" OR "evidence-based" OR "research use" OR "knowledge exchange" OR "knowledge transfer" OR "policy learning") AND ("environmental policy" OR "environmental governance" OR "sustainability policy" OR "biodiversity policy" OR "climate policy" OR "natural resource management")	19	12
4	Narrow combined PICO search	("science-policy interface" OR "science policy interface" OR "science-policy relationship" OR "scientific advice" OR "science advice" OR "advisory body" OR "knowledge brokering" OR "knowledge broker*" OR "co-production" OR "knowledge co-production") AND ("policy department*" OR "government agenc*" OR "public administration" OR "policy maker*" OR policymaker* OR "decision maker*" OR "public sector") AND ("evidence use" OR "evidence uptake" OR "research use" OR "research utilisation" OR "research utilization" OR "evidence-informed policy" OR "evidence-based policy" OR "knowledge utilisation" OR "knowledge utilization" OR "policy learning") AND ("environmental policy" OR "sustainability policy" OR "biodiversity policy" OR "climate policy" OR "environmental governance" OR "natural resource management")	16	11

Appendix B: Traffic Light System for Study Relevance and Quality

Table B1. *Traffic Light System Used to Assess Study Relevance and Quality Against the PICO Question*

Colour	Relevancies	Qualities
Green	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Directly answers the PICO question. 2. Focuses on science-policy relationships, advisory bodies, knowledge brokering, co-production, or evidence-use processes. 3. Relates to environmental, sustainability, biodiversity, climate, or natural resource policy. 4. Clearly shows how evidence is used, translated, or applied in policy. 	<p>Peer-reviewed journal article or review from a high-quality source.</p> <p>Clear method, strong relevance to environmental policy, and transparent discussion of findings and limitations.</p>
Yellow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Partly answers the PICO question. 2. Discusses science-policy relationships, evidence use, or knowledge exchange, but not always in an environmental policy context. 3. Provides useful background but is a weaker fit for the review question. 	<p>Peer-reviewed article or review with some limitations, such as broader policy focus, less direct evidence-use outcomes, or limited methodological detail.</p>
Red	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Does not answer the PICO question. 2. Does not focus on science-policy relationships, advisory arrangements, environmental policy, or evidence use. 3. Is too broad, unrelated, or not useful for this review. 	<p>Not peer-reviewed, commentary/opinion only, unclear method, weak evidence base, or insufficient connection to the review question.</p>

Table B2. *Full-Text Exclusion Reasons and Final Reassessment Outcomes.*

Exclusion stage / reason	Number	Articles counted here
Not focused on environmental or sustainability policy	1	Akerlof et al. (2025)
Did not examine science-policy relationships or advisory arrangements	3	Assmuth & Lyytimäki (2015); Dubuc et al. (2025); Eroğlu & Erbil (2022)
Did not address evidence use or evidence uptake	0	—
Not OECD or comparable democratic policy context	4	Carneiro & da-Silva-Rosa (2011); Donadelli (2020); Metzger et al. (2024); Schmidt et al. (2024)
Full text unavailable	0	—
Perspective/commentary rather than empirical or review evidence	5	Heidenreich et al. (2025); Guimarães Pereira and Saltelli (2017); Kowarsch et al. (2016); Rose et al. (2020); Stevance et al. (2020)
Too broad or not sufficiently aligned with PICO	6	Lidskog (2014); Mahony (2013); Pallett and Chilvers (2015); Rantala et al. (2024); Sarkki et al. (2020); Wiegler and Bruns (2025)
Subtotal: full-text articles excluded after eligibility assessment	19	—
Final relevance/quality reassessment: relevant, but weaker fit than retained studies	7	Bukowski (2017); Gustafsson and Lidskog (2018); Hofmann et al. (2025); Nyboer et al. (2021); Nyboer et al. (2025); Parviainen et al. (2022); Sager et al. (2020)
Total excluded after full-text assessment and reassessment	26	—

Note. Excluded studies are listed by author and year only; full details were retained in the screening record but omitted because they were not included in the final synthesis.

Appendix C: Collation Table

Table C1. Summary of 18 included studies examining science-policy relationships and evidence use in environmental policy development across OECD and comparable democratic contexts. Quality assessment uses a traffic-light system: green = high quality/strong PICO fit; yellow = moderate quality/partial fit.

Study	Country / Policy Area	Science-Policy Relationship Type	Evidence-Use Outcome	Key Finding Relevant to RQ	Quality	Comment
Averchenkova et al. (2021a)	UK; Climate Change Act.	Climate law integrating expert advisory responsibilities and carbon budgeting requirements.	Climate policy became more organised, long-term, and evidence based.	Formal climate laws should integrate expert advice into regular policy frameworks. The key mechanism is the statutory obligation, not the relationship itself. In contexts where advisory duties are legislated, evidence use becomes harder to ignore.	High	Strong fit for the RQ. Interview-based, which adds depth. The focus on one UK law limits transferability. Useful for understanding how legislation operates through legal structure rather than informal trust.
Averchenkova et al. (2021b)	UK; Parliament and Climate Change Committee.	Independent statutory climate advisory body.	Committee evidence was actively used in parliamentary climate debates.	Independent advisory bodies can provide credible, trusted evidence that strengthens policy accountability, particularly where their obligation and independence are clearly outlined. The statutory basis of the	High	Very relevant to the RQ. Strong empirical grounding in parliamentary records. The UK-specific context is a limitation, but the accountability mechanism is transferable to other OECD systems including Victoria.

Study	Country / Policy Area	Science-Policy Relationship Type	Evidence-Use Outcome	Key Finding Relevant to RQ	Quality	Comment
				Committee appears to be central to its influence.		
Cvitanovic et al. (2025)	Multiple countries; environmental science-policy contexts.	Knowledge brokers linking researchers, experts, and decision-makers	Improved knowledge exchange and evidence usability.	Knowledge brokers can help close the science-policy gap, but their effectiveness depends on institutional positioning, trust, and access. Impact is difficult to measure, and the field lacks consistent outcome reporting.	High	Strong systematic review. Useful for understanding brokerage as a formalisation mechanism. Very broad findings.
Dunn et al. (2018)	Australia; Melbourne urban water policy	Collaborative science-policy interface between researchers and planners.	Science informed urban water planning and decision-making.	The combination of relationships, timing, and co-production helped science become genuinely useful for policy. None of these factors was sufficient on their own.	High	Highly relevant and well-evidenced case study. The Victorian context adds direct relevance to Biodiversity 2037. The single-city and single-sector scope is a limitation, but the findings on co-production are broadly relevant.
Dupont et al. (2024)	European Union; climate policy	Formal and informal science-policy knowledge exchange.	Evidence entered policy through expert groups, impact assessments, and	Formal structures supported evidence uses, but politicisation can constrain informal exchange. Specifically, where advisory roles become politicised or constrained. The EU context illustrates that the creation of	High	Strong fit with broad EU-level focus. Particularly useful for understanding the tension between formal and informal contexts.

Study	Country / Policy Area	Science-Policy Relationship Type	Evidence-Use Outcome	Key Finding Relevant to RQ	Quality	Comment
			research networks.	formal structures alone does not guarantee independence.		
Gilson et al. (2025)	United States; Colorado River Basin	Boundary organisations linking science, policy, and practice.	Science informed monitoring, adaptation, and management decisions.	Boundary organisations help translate science into action, but uncertainty, budget constraints, and stakeholder disagreement can limit uptake. The Colorado Basin context also shows that even well-designed advisory structures can be undermined by resource limitations.	High	Strong empirical fit. The focus on one river basin is a limitation and less directly transferable. Uncertain management and resource constraints are recognisable across environmental governance contexts.
Greenhalgh et al. (2022)	New Zealand and California; freshwater policy	Scientist–decision-maker relationships in contested policy settings.	Identified factors shaping the influence of science in contested freshwater decision-making.	Trust, communication clarity, and decision-maker capacity shaped whether evidence influenced policy. This is notable because it suggests formalisation has limits when trust is absent or capacity is low. Structured relationships may still fail to deliver evidence uptake.	High	Relevant empirical study. Less focused on formal advisory bodies than other included studies, but its findings on trust and capacity are an important counterpoint.

Study	Country / Policy Area	Science-Policy Relationship Type	Evidence-Use Outcome	Key Finding Relevant to RQ	Quality	Comment
Kaufman and Boxshall (2023)	Australia and USA; environmental regulation.	Internal science experts integrated within regulatory agencies.	Science supported evidence-informed regulatory decisions.	Internal experts improve evidence use most effectively when they actively translate science for general audiences and policy makers. Positioning these experts within agencies rather than outside them appears to be central to effectiveness.	High	Strong fit. Primarily based on positive case examples. Directly relevant to the Biodiversity 2037 context, where evidence integration gaps relate partly to scientific communication and positionality.
Kennedy (2018)	United States; California ocean and coastal management.	Boundary organisation supporting science advice for coastal decisions.	Strengthened timely, relevant, and credible advice for coastal management.	Boundary organisations can effectively help communication between experts, stakeholders, and policy makers. However, their success depends on sustained funding and clear institutional purpose. The California case illustrates how boundary organisations operate in practice, though outcome measurement is limited.	Moderate	Useful fit. More conceptual and case-based than directly outcome-focused, which limits confidence in the findings. The moderate quality rating reflects that this conceptual framing is valuable, but practical claims are less rigorously established.
Lalor and Hickey (2014)	Canada, Australia, New Zealand,	Environment agencies and senior	Science informed executive decision-making	Evidence use improves where science is credible, clearly communicated, timely, and translated for ministers. The Westminster focus is particularly	High	Strong empirical fit with broad government-level focus. Key study for comparative Victorian policy context.

Study	Country / Policy Area	Science-Policy Relationship Type	Evidence-Use Outcome	Key Finding Relevant to RQ	Quality	Comment
	Ireland, and UK.	officials advising ministers.	across Westminster-based systems of government.	relevant, as it provides direct comparison to the context in which Biodiversity 2037 operates.		The multi-country scope strengthens its application.
Owens (2012)	UK; Royal Commission on Environmental Pollution.	Independent expert environmental advisory body with long-term authority.	Influenced environmental policy, legislation, and policy learning over decades.	Trusted, independent advisory bodies can support long-term evidence that improvised or informal arrangements cannot. The Commission's longevity and credibility were important, yet its eventual abolition also emphasises the institutional vulnerability of such bodies.	High	Strong advisory-body case study. Historical and UK-specific, which limits direct application. However, the account of how independence and credibility were built and then lost is important for understanding what makes formalised arrangements stable.
Pullin et al. (2016)	Europe; biodiversity and ecosystem services policy.	Knowledge coordination linking scientists, decision-makers, and evidence reviewers.	Matched synthesis methods to policy needs and constraints.	Evidence is more useful when synthesis methods are chosen to fit the policy scope, timeframe, and level of uncertainty. This highlights that policy timing, institutional, and decision context influence whether evidence synthesis is useful for decision-making.	Moderate	Relevant to evidence-use processes. The framing is a partial fit for the RQ. Moderate quality reflects that this study is valuable for understanding what makes evidence useful but does not directly examine science-policy relationships.

Study	Country / Policy Area	Science-Policy Relationship Type	Evidence-Use Outcome	Key Finding Relevant to RQ	Quality	Comment
Richards (2019)	Canada; municipal, provincial, and federal climate policy.	Climate science-policy relationships between research organisations and government.	Science influenced policy mainly through learning, increased awareness, and improved networks.	Stronger science-policy relationships help evidence enter policy, but political support remains necessary for genuine change. Evidence may inform policy discussion without necessarily leading to action when broader political conditions are weak.	High	Strong fit. Useful because it shows the limits of formalised relationships, not just their benefits. The finding that political support is still required is an important quality for this review's inclusion.
Runhaar and van Nieuwaal (2010)	Netherlands; Dutch Wadden Sea fisheries and gas mining.	Science-policy interface involving scientists, stakeholders, decision-makers, and mediators.	Evidence was initially ignored or used strategically, then later informed policy after reframing and legal changes.	Helps explain evidence failure, as evidence use improved only once the issue was reframed and structural changes created new incentives. Formalisation alone did not drive uptake, as institutional contexts had to change first.	High	The contested Dutch setting shows that science-policy relationships can be present without being effective. Directly relevant to understanding why Biodiversity 2037 may struggle to use evidence well even where advisory relationships exist without structural change.

Study	Country / Policy Area	Science-Policy Relationship Type	Evidence-Use Outcome	Key Finding Relevant to RQ	Quality	Comment
Saarela and Söderman (2015)	Finland; national energy and climate strategy impact assessment.	Knowledge exchange between ministries, policy officers, and assessing officers.	Impact assessment evidence was only partially used in policy development.	Evidence use improves when actors clarify necessary requirements early and coordinate assessment timing with the policy cycle. Where these conditions were absent, rigorous assessments were produced ineffectively.	High	Strong case study. The focus is on impact assessment processes rather than advisory bodies, but the findings on timing and coordination are directly relevant. Partial evidence use as an outcome is a realistic result that adds nuance to the review.
Seibicke (2025)	IPCC, UK Climate Change Committee, and EU Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change.	Climate scientific advisory bodies with different mandates, autonomy, and policy relations.	Scientific advice supported policy assessment, target-setting, and accountability.	Institutional design shapes how effectively advisory bodies provide credible and policy-relevant evidence. The analysis of three bodies shows that mandate clarity, operational independence, and access to decision-makers all collectively matter and intersect rather than operate independently.	High	Very strong advisory-body fit. The cross-body comparison is useful and directly addresses the RQ's focus in institutional design.
Sundqvist and Linke (2024)	International climate and fisheries governance;	International science advisory organisations	Advice uptake was clearer in fisheries than climate, but	Evidence use depends on both strong advisory links to decision-making and broader policy system integration. The fisheries and climate	Moderate	Useful conceptual comparison. Moderate rating is due to this paper being more theoretical than outcome-focused. The comparison adds value but reduces fit

Study	Country / Policy Area	Science-Policy Relationship Type	Evidence-Use Outcome	Key Finding Relevant to RQ	Quality	Comment
	IPCC and ICES.	linked to policy uptake systems.	neither guaranteed policy action.	comparison is useful, as ICES advice is more frequently acted on than IPCC advice, suggesting that context influences results.		with the environmental policy focus of the RQ.
Wagner et al. (2023)	Environmental sustainability policy; systematic review of 69 articles and 93 science-policy interface cases	Structured science-policy interfaces including expert groups, research projects, agencies, and interest groups.	Science-policy interface influenced learning, context, and policy formulation.	Effective science-policy interfaces require credibility, relevance, legitimacy, participation, interdisciplinarity, and clear communication.	High	Broadest scope of any included study. The scope means it is less focused on specific advisory mechanisms, but its synthesis of 93 cases makes it a particularly robust case study about science-policy interfaces effectiveness.

